

**Gender Indicators of the
Ibero-American Model of
Sport and Physical Activity
for Sustainable Development**

**Report on Countries of the First and
Second Phase of the Pilot Study**

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Introduction

In Latin America, research has shown that 39% of adults and 85% of adolescents do not meet the recommended levels of physical activity (Aguilar-Farías et al., 2018; Ferrari et al., 2020; Guthold et al., 2018). Studies also highlight significant gender disparities in physical activity. For example, a large-scale study involving more than 200,000 Latin American children and adolescents revealed that boys are more likely than girls to meet the World Health Organization's recommendation of at least 60 minutes of moderate-to-vigorous physical activity per day (Brazo-Sayavera et al., 2021).

Among adults, data from the Latin American Nutrition and Health Study (ELANS) show that men engage in more moderate-to-vigorous physical activity and more physical activity overall than women. Physical inactivity was considerably more prevalent among women (47.7%) than among men (33.0%) (Ferrari et al., 2020).

Similarly, results from the South American Network of Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour (SAPASEN), which assessed physical activity and sedentary behaviour in six South American countries, indicate that men are more active in leisure and work contexts, while women tend to be more active during commuting. However, women still have higher levels of physical inactivity overall. Furthermore, higher educational attainment was associated with lower physical activity among men and young adults, a trend not observed in women or older age groups (Werneck et al., 2019).

Analysis of gender indicators of the Ibero-American model in the pilot study countries

This report details the status of the three indicators (I7, I8, I9) that specifically refer to the area of gender equality (SDG 5). The report provides an overview in the region based on the situation in five countries that carried out the phases of the pilot study for the implementation of the Ibero-American indicator model for sport and physical activity for sustainable development. Table 1 shows the values calculated for the three gender indicators (I7, I8, I9) for the countries in Phase I of the pilot (Chile, Ecuador, Costa Rica) and Phase II (Colombia, Peru) of the pilot (CID, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c, 2025d, 2025e).

Table 1. Value of gender indicators in five Ibero-American countries

Indicators	Chile	Ecuador	Costa Rica	Colombia	Peru
7. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs	0%	-	-	-	-
8. Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity	52.4%	48.6%	36.4%	36.36%	22%
9. Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population	42.9%	17.0%	15.3%	30,11% ¹	-

Note. Empty cells (-) indicate that no relevant values could be reported for the corresponding indicator. Data were obtained from (CID, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c, 2025d, 2025e).

Indicator 7, referring to the percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs, cannot be calculated in most countries. When it can be calculated (Chile), we see that the budget allocation is zero (0%).

Regarding indicator 8, referring to the percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity, we see a heterogeneous situation across the five countries. In two of them, the situation is close to parity with men (52.4% Chile; 48.6% Ecuador); in two of them, the figure is moderate but far from parity (36.4% Costa Rica; 36.36% Colombia); and in one of them, the figure is far from parity (22% Peru).

Considering indicator 9, which refers to the percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population, we find countries with a high percentage of this gap (42.9% Chile; 30.11% Colombia), referring to a substantially lower level of physical activity among women, and other countries where the percentage of the gender gap is small (17.0% Ecuador; 15.3% Costa Rica). Of the five countries, only Colombia was able to perform the disaggregated calculation by age (with the percentage gap being greatest in adolescence: 59.36%), and Peru was not able to obtain a value for this indicator.

¹ In most countries, the value for this indicator refers to populations over 18 years of age: Chile (population over 18 years); Ecuador (population between 18 and 69 years); Costa Rica (population over 19 years). However, Colombia was able to calculate this indicator disaggregated by age group. Thus, it obtained the following values: 30.11% (18 to 64 years); 59.36% (13 to 17 years); 27.37% (6 to 12 years); and 31.46% (3 to 5 years).

Gender indicators in the sports public policy documents of the five countries

To understand the level of awareness and importance that different countries place on gender-related issues addressed by the three indicators discussed above, a qualitative content analysis (Jones et al., 2013) was conducted on the sports public policy documents of the various countries. The public policy documents analyzed are as follows: “Política nacional de actividad física y deporte 2016-2025” (Ministerio del Deporte Chile, 2016); “Plan Decenal de la Cultura Física: Deporte, Educación Física y Recreación DEFIRE 2018 – 2028” (Ministerio del Deporte Ecuador, 2018); “La Política Nacional del Deporte, la Recreación y la Actividad Física 2020-2030 (PONADRAF)” (ICODER, 2020); “Plan Estratégico Sectorial. Deporte, recreación y actividad física” (Ministerio Deportes Colombia, 2023); “Política Nacional de Actividad Física, Recreación, Deporte y Educación Física” (Ministerio de Educación, 2022). Content coding was carried out using categories derived from the indicators themselves. The results of this analysis can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Presence of gender indicators in the public policies of five Ibero-American countries from the pilot study

Indicators	Chile	Ecuador	Costa Rica	Colombia	Peru
7. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs					
8. Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity					
9. Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population					

Note. In the color system used, green indicates the presence of that indicator category in the public policy document, and red indicates its absence.

Regarding the presence of the themes expressed by the indicators in the different public policy documents of the countries, we see disparate results depending on the indicator in question. Starting with I7, referring to the budget, we see how the vast majority of countries did address this issue in their public policy documents. Regarding I8, on women in management positions, the absence of this topic in most of the countries' public policy documents pointed towards a clear blind spot in the sport policies of the region. Finally, regarding I9, referring to the gender gap in practice, most countries mentioned this issue, which implies greater awareness of the problem throughout the region.

These results imply that gender equality is widely recognized as a policy issue, but countries emphasize different facets. Most countries focus on program funding and participation gaps, but very few on governance structures. This unevenness suggests partial but insufficient collaborative engagement across gender-focused institutions, such as national women's ministries, federations, and civil society groups.

Convergence between awareness and capacity to calculate the gender indicators by the countries

After analyzing the status of gender-related indicators in five Ibero-American countries, we can see a certain disparity between awareness of their importance in sports policy of the countries and their capacity to calculate them. The relationship between the capacity to calculate indicators and the presence of indicators in public policies is summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Relationship between the values of indicators linked to SDG 5 (gender equality) and the presence of such indicators in public policy documents in Chile, Ecuador, Costa Rica, Colombia, and Peru according to the Ibero-American model

Indicators	Chile	Ecuador	Costa Rica	Colombia	Peru
7. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs	0%	-	-	-	-
8. Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity	52.4%	48.6%	36.4%	36.36%	22%
9. Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population	42.9%	17.0%	15.3%	30,11%	-

Note. Empty cells (-) indicate that no relevant value could be reported for the corresponding indicator. The color coding of the cells is as follows: Green, if the indicator appears both in the policy document and if a value for the indicator has been calculated according to the IB model formulas; Yellow, if it appears in only one of the two cases (empty yellow cells (-) mean that the indicator was present in the document, but could not be calculated; a value in a yellow cell means that the indicator was not present in the document, although it could be calculated); Red, if it does not appear in either case.

Most countries are aware (as evidenced by public policy texts) of the gender gap linked to their population's physical and sports participation (19): women engage in less physical and sports activity and have higher levels of sedentary lifestyles. Most of these countries can also make a specific calculation of the percentage of this gender gap in their population.

Nonetheless, there is a lack of awareness of the gender gap linked to the presence of women in management positions (18). This circumstance contrast starkly with the capacity of all the countries to generate data on the percentage of women in management positions in sports governing bodies.

Regarding the issue of budgeting for gender programs (17), we find a real awareness on the issue (it is present in public policy of most of the countries) but an inability to obtain concrete monetary values.

Conclusion

Most countries analysed (Chile, Ecuador, Costa Rica, and Colombia) show a moderate or high convergence between awareness in the sport policy and capacity to calculate the indicators. This circumstance shows a strong alignment between collaborative intentions and the structures needed to track gender-related progress. These countries have more institutionalized gender policies in sport and clearer pathways for reporting gender participation or gender gaps. Peru, however, show a lower convergence between policy awareness and capacity to calculate indicators, signaling a more fragile collaborative governance around gender equality.

Taken together, these trends reflect significant gender-related SDG commitments into sport policy systems of most countries, illustrating a solid institutionalization of gender-focused collaboration.

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